
CHIMERA-LIKE STATES IN BALANCED NEURAL CIRCUITS

A PREPRINT

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ABSTRACT

For a long time network scientists have been delving into the dynamics of sparsely connected networks with the aim to understand the nature of temporal irregularity of cortical neurons. This temporal variability in firing has been corresponded to the emergence of a balanced state in large cortical networks - a state where the excitatory and inhibitory connections cancel each other leaving only the fluctuations that amount to the irregular spiking activity. We investigate this behaviour for different network settings. Another phenomenon that we investigate is the breakage of symmetry of the oscillator population where one part synchronizes and the other part oscillates incoherently. Such behavior has been called 'Chimera state' and has been observed a decade ago for the first time. In this project, we explored the balanced state in populations of spiking neurons. We investigated how the populations reach the asynchronous irregular and synchronous regular state. We then simulated networks of connected populations and investigated how to induce chimera like properties ¹.

Keywords Network Dynamics · Computational Neuroscience · Machine Learning

1 Introduction

In networks of identical non-locally coupled oscillators Kuramoto and Battogtokh [2002] discovered that part of the individual oscillators can synchronize, while the rest stays unsynchronized. This emergent behaviour has later been deemed a chimera state.

Chimera states have after that been observed in several other systems, e.g. in rings of non-locally coupled oscillators Abrams and Strogatz [2004], Abrams et al. [2008], Sethia et al. [2008], and in a system of mechanically coupled metronomes Martens et al. [2013].

These systems are, however, highly artificial. In our research project, we investigated the possibility of chimera states in more biologically inspired networks, namely balanced neural circuits.

Cortical circuits are huge networks of excitatory and inhibitory neurons, where every neuron receives large number (order of 1000 to 10000) of inputs from other cortical neurons. A lot of research has been done van Vreeswijk and Sompolinsky [1996], Vreeswijk and Sompolinsky [1998], Brunel [2000] to investigate how neurons receiving that many inputs still do not fire all the time (at their physiological limit) or not at all, but rather fire in a random manner following a Poisson distribution. Van Vreeswijk and Sompolinsky showed analytically in van Vreeswijk and Sompolinsky [1996], Vreeswijk and Sompolinsky [1998] that in networks where each neuron receives a large number of inputs that is small compared to number of neurons in the network (sparsely connected network), balance between excitatory and inhibitory

¹This is a documentation of results of a project completed in early 2015.

inputs can be maintained.

Brunel explored analytically and numerically what different states a large circuit of sparsely connected neurons can be in Brunel [2000], and found among them states in which neurons can synchronize in their firing as well as states in which neurons fire highly irregularly.

We tried to set up conditions in which one of two separated populations would be in one of those state, and the other population in the other state, to investigate stability of those states when there is a connection between both populations.

2 Theory and Methods

2.1 Leaky Integrate-and-Fire Model

The leaky integrate-and-fire (LIF) model is by far considered to be a best example of a formal spiking neuron model Gerstner and Kistler [2002]. As per this model an action potential occurs whenever the neuron membrane potential v reaches a threshold value V_Θ . After the action potential occurs the membrane potential is reset to a certain value below the threshold potential Dayan and Abbott [2001]. The standard form of leaky integrate-and-fire model Timme et al. [2003] is:

$$\frac{dv}{dt} = -\gamma v(t) + I, \quad (1)$$

where I is the driving current and γ is a leakage factor.

Figure 1: Membrane potential of a neuron. At $t = t_1$ the membrane potential V crosses the threshold potential which leads to a reset of the potential to $V = 0$, and a spike is emitted (Jahnke, Timme et al. 2009) Jahnke et al. [2009].

2.2 Balanced State Theory

Brain neurons trigger other neurons mostly by sending across electrical impulses called spikes. These spikes or action potentials are short lasting events which lead to the sudden rise and fall of the membrane potential. Neuronal circuits exhibit many different states ranging from regular highly synchronized spiking to highly irregular spiking. The firing patterns of the cortical neurons have been observed to exhibit a strong degree of temporal irregular spiking activity; however, when a constant current is injected into the population the spiking behavior becomes regular (Van Vreeswijk and Sompolinsky, 1996) van Vreeswijk and Sompolinsky [1996]. Up until early 90s, this has been a long standing paradox in cortical dynamics to understand the origin of this irregularity and its implications Douglas and Martin [1991], Ferster and Jagadeesh [1992]. Physiologically, neurons in the cortical circuits are known to receive thousands of synaptic connections and summing these signals should lead to an almost deterministic input to each neuron (and only weak random fluctuations) and ergo a regular spiking output. This contradicts with the observed temporal irregularity of the firing patterns of these cortical neurons.

In 1998 C. van Vreeswijk and H. Sompolinsky Vreeswijk and Sompolinsky [1998] proposed a hypothesis directed at this problem. According to them, the irregularity was due to the balance of excitatory and inhibitory currents into the cortical neurons for a wide range of parameters. This balance results in a net synaptic input whose mean and fluctuations are both of the order of the spiking threshold. Since the fluctuations of the synaptic input determine the

timing of the crossing of the spiking threshold, the firing pattern is highly irregular (van Vreeswijk and Sompolinsky, 1996) van Vreeswijk and Sompolinsky [1996].

2.3 Chimera States

Chimera states have been discovered a decade ago in which an array of identical oscillators split into two domains exhibiting different characteristics - one part is frequency-locked and coherent and the other desynchronised and incoherent at the same time Kuramoto and Battogtokh [2002], Abrams and Strogatz [2004]. Due to the the oscillators being identical we cannot know which oscillators are locked and which ones not except for their collective initial state.

2.4 Model

In collaboration with two other students from the lab, Diemut Regel and Francesca Schönsberg, we created a simulation of sparsely connected networks of leaky integrate-and-fire neurons in phase representation. All data shown in this report were created using this simulation. The source code is provided as supplementary material. Furthermore, a usage example is given in supplementary material (section B), too.

The simulation can be run with any numbers of internal populations. Neuron m in population i receives a connection from neuron n in population j (directed connection from m to n) with probability

$$p(j) = \frac{K}{N_j}, \quad (2)$$

where N_j is the number of neurons in population j . Thus, on average each neuron in population i receives connections from K neurons in population j , as in van Vreeswijk and Sompolinsky [1996], Vreeswijk and Sompolinsky [1998]. K should be chosen to be much smaller than the number of neurons in any population, to guarantee sparseness of the network. The strength of connections from neurons in population j to neurons in population i is $J_{int}^{i,j}$, where the matrix J_{int} defining connection strengths between internal populations needs to be specified manually before running a simulation. Note that $J_{int}^{i,j}$ will not be divided by \sqrt{K} as in van Vreeswijk and Sompolinsky [1996], Vreeswijk and Sompolinsky [1998] in course of the simulation, but will remain as it is provided by the user.

Neurons in the model are LIF neurons in phase representation Jahnke et al. [2009], Timme et al. [2003]. Neuron n 's state at time t is determined by its phase, $\phi_n(t) \in (-\infty, 1]$. Without any input from other neurons, the phases evolves as

$$\frac{d}{dt}\phi_n = 1. \quad (3)$$

Upon reaching $\phi_n(t_{spike}) = 1$, neuron n will emit a spike. If there is a connection of strength $\varepsilon_{m,n}$ from neuron n to neuron m , the spike leads to a jump of $\varepsilon_{m,n}$ in membrane potential at time $t = t_{spike} + \tau$, where the delay τ between emitting and receiving is the same for all connections. The membrane potential $U_m(\phi_m)$ depends on the neurons phase ϕ_m . To account for a jump in membrane potential in phase representation, we use the transfer function, $H(\phi_m, \varepsilon) = U^{-1}(U(\phi_m(t_{spike} + \tau)) + \varepsilon_{m,n})$, as in Timme et al. [2003]. For the LIF model $U(\phi_m)$ is

$$U(\phi_m) = \frac{I_m}{\gamma_m} \left(1 - \left(1 - \frac{\gamma_m}{I_m} \right)^{\phi_m} \right), \quad (4)$$

where the parameters I_m and γ_m are same for all neurons in one population (see also equation 1).

Neuron m can receive spikes from more than one neuron at the same instant, in which case their contributions are first added up to a total jump in potential of

$$\varepsilon_m = \sum_{n \in Spike(t_{spike})} \varepsilon_{m,n}, \quad (5)$$

where $Spike(t_{spike})$ is the set of internal neurons that emitted a spike at time $t = t_{spike}$ and external neurons (for which we only consider the arrival time of spikes, not emission time) whose spikes arrive at $t = t_{spike} + \tau$.

In the simulation this is done for all neurons in one step (with number of internal neurons N_{int} and number of external neurons N_{ext}),

$$\varepsilon = (\varepsilon)_1 : \varepsilon_{N_{int}} = W \cdot v(t_{spike}), \quad (6)$$

multiplying weight matrix W ,

$$W = (\varepsilon_{m,n}); \quad m \in \{1, 2, \dots, N_{int}\}; \quad n \in \{1, 2, \dots, N_{int} + N_{ext}\}, \quad (7)$$

with spike vector $v(t_{spike}) \in \mathbb{Z}^{N_{int}+N_{ext} \times 1}$, where $v_i = 1$ if $i \in Spike(t_{spike})$ and $v_i = 0$ else.

If a neuron's phase would exceed 1 after receiving spikes, it is considered to immediately emit a spike and its phase is reset to 0.

If not stated otherwise the initial phase at time $t = 0$ is drawn randomly from a uniform distribution between 0 and 1 for each internal neuron.

3 Results

3.1 Single inhibitory population

Our aim is to reach to a chimera-like state. For this we need to explore the conditions for having a balanced and a synchronous state. We start with a simple inhibitory population and try to get to a balanced state. The setup for this is shown in figure 2.

Figure 2: Single inhibitory population with external input.

For exploring the balanced state we have an external population driving a network of recurring inhibitory population. The external input behaves in a poissonian way. According to Brunel Brunel [2000] the most influential parameter for getting a balanced state is the ratio between the inhibitory and the excitatory coupling - with stronger inhibition than excitation it is possible to get to a balanced state (Brunel, 2000) Brunel [2000]. If we look at the figure(number), we can clearly see that most of the neurons fire irregularly and account for the network being in the balanced state. Some of the neurons are suppressed and do not fire at all.

CV

The cv plot is equally distributed around 1.0 which also corresponds to a poisson process. If we exclude the extreme cases on the left side - these neurons are not firing or it could even be the case that they firing absolutely regular.

3.2 Inhibitory and excitatory populations

In case of a population of oscillators with exclusively excitatory connections, the oscillators begin to group together as the system evolves. As the group gets larger, it produces a larger collective pulse as it fires. This brings more oscillators to threshold along with it. So in this way the bigger group tends to "absorb" the other oscillators. This absorption continues until we reach a point when only one group remains - at this point, the population is synchronized Mirollo and Strogatz [1990]. Since the system of one inhibitory population I with external poissonian input does not give us enough control over I , we introduced an excitatory population E and connected it with I . Our idea behind it was, that the excitatory population would synchronize if there wasn't enough inhibitory feedback from I . In the systems described here, both I and E received input from the same external population, as drawn in figure 4(b). E should be able to drive I to synchrony, if $J_{I,E}$ was large enough. Furthermore, this system is similar to the original one of Vreeswijk and Sompolinsky [1998] and easily put into a balanced state.

Figure 7 shows an example of such a system in balanced state. In figure 7(a) shows spike trains of 30 randomly chosen neurons per population. Figure 7(b) shows the CV for the system.

When the recurrent connection $J_{E,E}$ of the excitatory population is increased and the inhibitory feedback $J_{E,I}$ does not compensate it, the excitatory population will eventually synchronize. These strong synchronized excitatory pulses can, depending on connection strength $J_{I,E}$, cause the inhibitory population to synchronize. An example of both populations synchronized is shown in figure 8. The initial phase of neurons in E was set to $\phi_i = 0.999$, such that they would almost immediately fire together as soon as the simulation started.

One can see in figure 8(a) that most of the neurons in I are synchronized and fire regularly. They are, however, not in complete synchrony with neurons in E . They spike only at every second synchronous spike of population E . Neurons in E , meanwhile, spike once per τ .

The CV in figure 8(b) resembles the regularity of the firing pattern. Although it is cut off in this plot, around 400 neurons ($\approx 50\%$) of population I and (almost) all neurons in population E exhibit ISIs with a CV of 0.

(a) Spike trains for 50 neurons of population I . Parameters: $K = 40$, $J_{int} = -0.8$, $J_{ext} = 0.3$, $I = 4$, $rate = 1$, $\gamma = 1$, $N_I = 800$.

(b) cv

(c) phases

Figure 3: Spike trains for 50 neurons of population I .

In contrast to the previous system, figure 9 shows a system where E is synchronized and fires once per τ , and where I fires more or less irregularly. Neurons in I fire however, favorably in discrete steps, as can be seen in the more zoomed in plot of the spike trains in figure 5. They tend to fire, not surprisingly, most likely when neurons in E fire, too. In that, though, they seem to fire irregularly (and not, e.g. regularly at every second or third spike of population E .)

3.3 Two connected inhibitory populations

In this network we have two inhibitory and two excitatory populations - $I1$ and $I2$ are inhibitory and $E1$ and $E2$ are excitatory populations respectively (see sketch in figure 6). This network consists of 2 networks as in figure, which we intended to connect via the inhibitory populations. We started exploring the dynamics without using external inputs, and actually found results worth presenting only in this special case without external input. In figure 10 we first show

Figure 4: Inhibitory and excitatory population.

an example of both sides of the network not connected via I1 and I2, so $J_{I_i, I_j} = 0$ for $i \neq j$. One side (I1 and E1) show synchronous behaviour, due to similar reasons as in figure 7. E1 has relatively strong recurrent connections and since it is excitatory, this leads to absorption process and makes the population essentially a clock as we can see in the figure 10(a). Since E1 has an excitatory connection to I1, this synchrony is also passed on to I1 as we can see in the figure. I2 and E2, meanwhile, fire more or less irregularly.

In the example in figure 11, conditions are very similar, but now I1 and I2 are connected. There is only a weak connection between the inhibitory populations, so the synchrony is not really passed on to the population I2. Populations I2 and E2 fire quite irregularly. We choose the synaptic strengths of populations I2 and E2 relatively strong because according to Kriener [16] if we have stronger synapses this increases the coefficient of variation. This we did to counter balance the regular input to I1. Maybe we overdid it a bit because if we look at the figure 11(b), it seems to be totally irregular – more irregular than a poisson process.

4 Discussion

The approaches we chose were quick and simple numerical ones based on our intuition. We feel that we created a great basis for continuing research, and focused on usability and description of our simulation. Our approaches did, however, not lead us to results that go far beyond the expected outcome.

The system of one inhibitory population with an irregular external population (section 3.1) is very easy to balance, and was a good starting point to get a feeling for the simulation and balanced networks. Too little connection strength from external to internal population would lead to very regular firing. Increasing connection strength more and more would, on the other hand, drive the CV higher and higher. It will also drive it higher than 1, but we are not really sure why, since the driving external inputs' ISIs have a CV of around 1.

To be able to induce synchrony in the inhibitory population, we added an excitatory population to the system (section 3.2). This set-up is very similar to that of van Vreeswijk and Sompolinsky [1998], and thus a known and investigated set-up. We were able to synchronize it (figure 8) as well as to balance it (figures 7 and 9), and thought this might be the simplest set-up of sparsely connected networks to find chimera-like states.

The balance in figure 9 is different from *real* balanced states, however, since the inhibitory population spikes only in discrete steps. Its purpose was only to create a somewhat balanced network that shares most of the parameters with the synchronized network in figure 8, to investigate if chimera states could emerge among *almost* identical connected networks. The parameters still differ, however, in connections $J_{E,I}$ and $J_{I,E}$ between population E and I . We did not find any set of parameters, for which we could bring the system to balance as well as to synchrony by only changing initial conditions (e.g. by starting the phases once in synchrony and once in a random fashion).

In case of synchrony (figure 8), population I emits a spike only at every second regular spike of E . We assume the simple explanation for this is that the previous inhibitory spike compensates the excitatory spike of E enough to

Figure 5: Zoomed in to figure 9(a).

Figure 6: Two connected networks.

suppress a possible spike (due to the strong recurrent connection of $J_{I,I} = -0.8$ compared to the excitatory connection of $J_{I,E} = 0.4$).

Our results closest to chimera like-states were not produced with external input. So we were only able to find results worth presenting in the special case of no external inputs in the network shown in figure 6. We think similar states should also be possible in networks with external inputs, but we did not explore the parameter space enough to come up with results of any use yet.

The inhibitory populations in the example shown in figure 11 are not identical, so this does not correspond to a state that we can call chimera. Furthermore, we decided in advance which side should synchronize and which should be irregular. This shows, however, the possibility of having both states quite stable even when inter-connected.

We think another quite different set-up worth exploring could be a sparse network of multiple populations, where next neighbours receive more or stronger connection than next next neighbours and so on, to emulate a decrease in

coupling strength as seen in other works on chimera states Kuramoto and Battogtokh [2002], Abrams and Strogatz [2004], Abrams et al. [2008] in terms of clusters in the network. This would, however, require more computational power and probably more time than we had available for this project.

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A Plots

(a) Spike trains of 30 neurons per population.

(b) Histogram of CV of ISIs for both populations.

Figure 7: Example of I and E in balance. $N_I = 800, N_E = 800, N_{ext} = 800, K = 40, J_{ext}^I = 0.1, J_{ext}^E = 0.1,$
 $rates_{ext} = 1.0, \tau = 0.01.$

(a) Spike trains of 30 neurons per population.

(b) Histogram of CVs of the ISIs for both populations.

Figure 8: Example of I in synchrony due to synchronous drive by E . Phases of neurons in E initialized in synchrony. $N_I = 800, N_E = 800, N_{ext} = 400, K = 40, J_{I,I} = -0.8, J_{I,E} = 0.4, J_{E,I} = -0.1, J_{E,E} = 0.42, J_{ext}^I = 0.4, J_{ext}^E = 0.4, rate_{ext} = 1.0, \tau = 0.01$.

(a) Spike trains of 30 neurons per population.

(b) Histogram of CVs of the ISIs for both populations.

Figure 9: Example of I in 'balance' while E is in a synchronous regular state. Phases of neurons in E initialized in synchrony. $N_I = 800, N_E = 800, N_{ext} = 400, K = 40, J_{I,I} = -0.8, J_{I,E} = 0.05, J_{E,I} = -0.44, J_{E,E} = 0.38, J_{ext}^I = 0.4, J_{ext}^E = 0.4, rate_{ext} = 1.0, \tau = 0.01$.

(a) Spike trains: Pop. I1 and I2 are inhibitory. Pop. E1 and E2 are excitatory. This figure shows the spike trains of 30 neurons in each population.

(b) Histogram of CVs of the ISIs for all populations.

Figure 10: Example of network in 6 with I1 and I2 not connected ($J_{I_1, I_2} = J_{I_2, I_1} = 0$). Parameters: $N_{I_1}, N_{I_2}, N_{E_1}, N_{E_2} = 1000$, $J_{I_1, I_1} = -.12$, $J_{I_1, E_1} = .11$, $J_{I_1, I_2} = 0$, $J_{E_1, I_1} = -.12$, $J_{E_1, E_1} = .14$, $J_{I_2, I_1} = 0$, $J_{I_2, I_2} = -.12$, $J_{I_2, E_2} = .11$, $J_{E_2, I_2} = -.13$, $J_{E_2, E_2} = .11$.

(a) Spike trains: Pop. I1 and I2 are inhibitory. Pop. E1 and E2 are excitatory. This figure shows the spike trains of 30 neurons in each population.

(b) Histogram of CVs of the ISIs for all populations.

Figure 11: Example of network in 6 showing Chimera like properties. Parameters: $N_{I_1}, N_{I_2}, N_{E_1}, N_{E_2} = 1000$, $J_{I_1, I_1} = -.12$, $J_{I_1, E_1} = .11$, $J_{I_1, I_2} = -0.05$, $J_{E_1, I_1} = -.12$, $J_{E_1, E_1} = .2$, $J_{I_2, I_1} = -0.05$, $J_{I_2, I_2} = -.20$, $J_{I_2, E_2} = .18$, $J_{E_2, I_2} = -.20$, $J_{E_2, E_2} = .18$.

B Usage example simulation

The code for this project can be found at <https://github.com/ilyasku/sparsenetworks>. To run an example simulation, there is a module named **sn_example_simulation.py** that can be found in the **scripts** directory of the repository. We ran our simulations with Python 2.7.6 but it should also be possible to run with older versions or Python 3.x. It requires numpy and scipy to be installed, and the plot scripts require matplotlib.

The example sets up a simulation of two inhibitory populations with external input. To run the example, just navigate to the **Scripts** folder and call:

```
python example_simulation.py
```

This should start the simulation and show its progress. When it reaches 100%, the phases and spikes will be written to .npy-files into the folder **out_example**.

To view the output, you can use the script named **plot_output_separate.py**. We recommend using it with ipython, since we did not put in commands to keep the plot windows open in python. Start ipython in the command line and type:

```
run plot_output_seperate.py out_example -show
```

This should pop up some plots: a plot of spike trains for 30 random neurons per population, a plot of the CV for all neurons (for which it is possible), a plot of the rates for each population, and a plot showing phases of 5 randomly chosen neurons per population. The script takes at least one argument, namely the output folder. In this case that is **out_example**. The second argument is optional, it can be either **-show** or **-save** (or you can use both, one as second the other as third argument), which tells the script to either only show the plots or to only save them in the specified folder (or both).

If you do not have ipython installed, you can still use python to only save the plots, this should not cause any problems:

```
python plot_output_separate.py -save
```

For any further usage we recommend starting with the file **sn_example_simulation.py** and adapting it to your needs. The code itself (the file for the simulation is **sparsenetworks/system.py**, for reading the data it is **sparsenetworks/output_analyzer.py**) is documented, and hopefully in such a way that it is usable without much effort. In addition, there is a not yet complete documentation we created using doxygen in the folder **sparsenetworks/Documentation**. To view the html version of it in a browser, click on the file **html/index.html**.